

2-Mercaptobenzimidazole as a Corrosion Inhibitor for Copper and Brass in Chlorosubstituted Acetic Acids

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2-Mercaptobenzimidazole (2-MBMA) is investigated as an inhibitor of corrosion for copper and brass in 0.1N acetic acid, 0.1N monochloroacetic acid, 0.1N dichloroacetic acid, and 0.1N trichloroacetic acid. The performance of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole as an inhibitor is found fairly good and it affords adequate protection to copper and brass.

IN the Gujarat state chloroacetic acid is manufactured and utilized in cellulose industry. It appears that extensive corrosion problem has to be faced in industrial practice. The object of the investigation is to suggest an effective inhibitor like 2-mercaptobenzimidazole when vessels of metals and alloys are used with these acids.

For the immersion of specimen 250 ml solutions of 0.1N chloroacetic acids were employed. Experiments were carried out for 2 days at $30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. The influence of current densities on the system was also carried out as described earlier^{2,3,4}. The concentration of the inhibitor used was 200 ppm which gave maximum protection. The results are given in table 1, and are depicted in Figs. 1 & 2.

COPPER FIG.1

The purpose of this paper is thus to describe practical application of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole to copper and brass, and to record the results of investigation into the fundamental mechanism involved in the protection.

Experimental

Copper sheets (26 S. W. G.) of the composition of Cu 99.6%, Fe and other metals 0.4%, brass sheets (26 S. W. G.) of the composition of Cu 63.2%, Zn 36.6%, Sn 0.07%, Pb 0.01% and Fe traces were employed for study. They had been cold rolled and annealed at about 550°. They were employed for the loss in weight data. Rectangular specimens of area 3×6 cm with a small hole of about 1 mm diameter just near the upper edge of the specimen for suspension, were cleaned and polished as usual.

BRASS (63/37) FIG.2

2-Mercaptobenzimidazole : 2-mercaptobenzimidazole $C_7H_6N_2S$, having a molecular weight of 150 has the following structural formula :

It is available commercially as a purified and commercial quality powder, the powder form melts at $296^{\circ}-8^{\circ}$. It is soluble in alcohol and dioxan and less soluble in water. It is stable in caustic alkalis. There is no significant toxic hazard, with 2-mercaptobenzimidazole.

When added to nearly neutral solutions of cupric and zinc salts, aqueous solutions of Na-2-mercaptobenzimidazole produce precipitates which are insoluble in water and in many organic liquids.

Discussion :

The inhibitive power of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole in general increases with increase in concentration of the inhibitor. The concentration of 200 ppm is effective in 0.1N chloroacetic acids for copper and brass. It is suggested that 2-mercaptobenzimidazole is a fairly good inhibitor for copper and its alloys.

A large number of workers have studied nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocyclic organic compounds as an inhibitor for copper and its alloys. In recent investigation it has become recognised that some of the more bonded organic inhibitors, such as 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, 1,2,3 benzotriazole and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole undergo chemical reaction at the metal surface to form chemisorbed two dimensional barriers of a molecular order of thickness. It is suggested that corrosion inhibitors clearly operate by becoming closely associated with the surface of the metal and inhibitor effectiveness should be related to the strength of the metal-inhibitor bond, the stronger the bond attachment the greater will be the efficiency obtained and also the degree of permanence. These properties are likely to be associated with triazole and thiazole rings and it was necessary to establish which of the nitrogen and sulphur atoms were responsible for the inhibition and also the mercapto (-SH) group⁵.

The present investigation is carried out regarding corrosion inhibiting properties of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole in chloroacetic acids for copper and brass. 2-mercaptobenzimidazole is a weak thio acid ionizing as

Fig. 4.

The ionic species form complexes with copper or zinc ions which act as a protective coating to the metal surface. There is strong evidence, therefore, that a true chemical bond is involved, similar to that observed when the insoluble complexes are formed in aqueous solution of Na-2-mercaptobenzimidazole with copper and zinc ions, involving chelation via nitrogen atom ofazole ring and sulphur atom containing the labile hydrogen atom.

It is considered that copper-2-mercaptobenzimidazole complex acts as an inhibitor as well as a physical barrier. It was suggested that the inhibition afforded by 2-mercaptobenzimidazole for copper and its alloys in acidic media due to the insoluble coherent, thin and nonporous complex film formation. Thus, its performance as corrosion inhibitor would depend on the stability, solubility, adhesivity and impenetrability of the film of the complex (chelate) formed on the metal specimens. Similar type of mechanism may be also visualised for zinc.

TABLE 1—LOSS BY WT. DATA FOR CORROSION OF COPPER AND BRASS (63/37) IN CHLOROSUBSTITUTED ACETIC ACIDS WITH 2-MERCAPTOBENZIMEDAZOLE

		Temperature ; $30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$		Duration : 2 days	
Medium	Concentration of inhibitor in p.p.m	Copper mg/dm ²	% Inhibition	Brass(63/37) mg/dm ²	% Inhibition
0.1N Acetic Acid	00	34.7	—	40.0	—
	10	4.7	88	18.6	54
	20	2.8	92	13.9	65
	40	1.4	96	8.9	78
	100	1.4	96	7.8	81
0.1N mono chloro-acetic acid	200	0.8	98	6.4	84
	00	54.2	—	51.6	—
	10	29.2	46	8.3	84
	20	27.8	49	6.9	87
	40	22.2	59	5.6	89
0.1N dichloro-acetic acid	100	19.4	64	5.6	89
	200	2.5	95	4.2	92
	00	61.6	—	58.3	—
	10	32.8	47	13.9	76
	20	29.7	52	6.9	88
0.1N trichloroacetic acid	40	24.8	60	5.0	91
	100	19.7	68	4.2	93
	200	19.4	68	4.2	93
	00	477.6	—	527.7	—
	10	232.5	51	10.8	98
0.1N trichloroacetic acid	20	75.8	84	2.7	99
	40	75.8	84	1.7	99
	100	63.0	87	1.4	100
	200	6.4	99	0.8	100

Application of Tafel equation : The rise of cathodic potential on the addition of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole may be due to the formation of insoluble film on cathode. This suggests that the anodic reaction is suppressed and that the cathodic reaction involving the reduction of oxygen is also inhibited. It should be noted that the cathodic potential is lowered to that of

FIG. 1 - A

LOG C.D. Amp/cm²
FIG. 2 - A

hydrogen discharge. It proves effectiveness of the retardation power of the inhibitor.

The cathodic potential will vary as determined by Tafel's rule or in other words, at the same cathodic potential, the apparent current density falls in presence of inhibitor (2-MBMA). By extrapolating Tafel's plot in presence of inhibitor, one can determine current density at steady state potential (Figs. 1-A & 2-A). The inhibitor efficiency agrees with the efficiency determined by loss in weight method using equation :

$$\% \text{ efficiency} = \frac{I_b - I_i}{I_b} \times 100$$

I_b = C.D. without inhibitor

I_i = C.D. with inhibitor

The inhibitor efficiency and Tafel's slope determined by Tafel's equation are shown in figures 1 & 2. The inhibitor efficiency calculated by the above equation is 99% and 100% respectively for copper and brass.

	Tafel's slope		% efficiency
	Blank	with 2-MBMA	
Copper	0.13	0.12	99
Brass	0.24	0.10	100

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